

HeartSelling

Developed by: METALOG® GmbH & Co. KG

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Keywords

Business, Business Ethics, Commerce, Competition, Conflict Management, Cooperation, Ethical Decision-making, Negotiation, Sustainability, Trading, Transparency

Figure 1. Photo from HeartSelling (METALOG® GmbH & Co. KG). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

HeartSelling (see Figure 1) promotes fair, value-based trade by balancing competition and cooperation. The objective is to initiate a discussion on value-oriented trade. It is aimed at sales and negotiation professionals, as well as teams looking to explore communication,

transparency, and cooperation. HeartSelling fulfills the components of a serious game by incorporating simulation, play, role, and learning (Schwägele, 2015, pp. 45 ff.).

Four competing teams share the same goal. They need to build a figure that requires different pieces. Each group specializes in producing a single component, which is why trade and cooperation are necessary. Under time pressure and with initially high levels of uncertainty, participants must both cooperate and pursue their individual goals simultaneously. After the trading phase, a monetary winner is crowned. A subsequent part with the group's self- and external assessments is added to the results. Fair and transparent teams receive an increase in points, while unfair teams sometimes have points deducted. This often shifts the winners and makes it clear that long-term success depends on value-oriented action.

The game was developed by "Metalog," a company specializing in soft-skills games.

Facts

Release date:	–
Developer:	METALOG® GmbH & Co. KG
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	8–24; optimum: 16
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	2–3 hours, depending on the depth of the discussion afterward. Time is independent of the number of players.
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Ideal setting: 1 room plus 4 group rooms; alternative: 1 large room with four separated zones with visual protection (privacy screens, pinboards, etc.).
Material:	All material is included with the one-time purchase of the game. In addition, a blackboard or flipchart is needed to track the results.
Price:	€537

Resonance & Criticism

HeartSelling is a relatively unknown game from the Metalog portfolio. This benefits its use in teaching, as the game mechanism only works if the participants are unfamiliar with it. There are no official evaluations of the game, as these are mainly used in practical educational work without research-based support. However, observations by facilitators and direct feedback from the players indicate a high level of involvement and comprehensibility of the game. The evaluation of soft factors is a surprise effect of the game that players sometimes criticize. However, this mechanism is needed for the game to work.

Game Principle & Process

The game is played with four teams that compete synchronously. They must interact and cooperate to achieve their individual goals. There are a few basic rules that cannot be influenced: the number and duration of the trading phases and a clearly defined trading zone. Beyond that, they are free to compete and cooperate as they wish. They can freely control both the handling of their own parts and the handling of their information. Pricing and exchange conditions are freely negotiable.

The game objectives and rules are announced at the beginning. The teams also have permanent access to brief instructions that state the game objectives. The main aim is to produce a complete figure. The importance of fairness for the game is mentioned casually. It is essential to include this to avoid post-game discussions. At the same time, the soft goals must not be overemphasized. The game mechanism needs the participants to pay little or no attention to them.

The game consists of several trading phases, followed by an evaluation of the figures produced. The monetary result is celebrated, and the end of the game is presented to the teams. From here on, an eye-opening experience sets in. The soft topics are questioned using evaluation forms, and the results are discussed in plenary. Each group expresses how they perceived the others in the game and names positive and negative experiences. This discussion reflects the primary learning process. This is where the link is made between short-term and long-term success and fair, value-oriented interactions. The fact that the assessment of social factors is included as a quantitative position in the overall game result underlines their relevance.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

HeartSelling emphasizes that individual goals cannot be achieved without cooperation and a value-based approach to interaction with other operators. The second message is that short-term success is often attractive and can tempt players to overlook sustainable, long-term success. The initial situation, time pressure, and high uncertainties ensure that the game works out. A big part of the learning experience takes place in the game discussion. All experiences gained during the main game phase are valuable and can contribute to the game's overall message.

It is possible to run the game alone; however, it is best to carry it out in pairs. This allows for making more external observations during the gaming phase, which can then enrich the debriefing phase. The facilitator's key role is to introduce the game and oversee timekeeping and moderation across the different rounds. During the game phase, the facilitator should act discreetly and not intervene unless a breach of complex rules occurs. The main challenge of the facilitator is to lead the debriefing. Each game is different, and unpredictable events can happen. A listening attitude that gives the players enough room to report their experiences is needed.

The game mechanisms are easy to understand. The game manufacturer provides detailed instructions and a video for the game. With sufficient preparation time, users can learn to execute the game themselves.

Effectiveness

There is no empirical evidence for the effectiveness of this specific game. However, it is used frequently because of direct, positive participant feedback. When asked for feedback, they emphasize the game's entertainment, its flow, and the hands-on experience with the discussed topics.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

In the beginning, the different teams have to form their identity. Therefore, they develop a name, logo, and slogan. Such creative tasks can sometimes be used for inappropriate, discriminatory “jokes”. The facilitator should prevent this at an early stage and address it during moderation.

The game itself does not address problematic or sensitive topics. The game materials and room setting do not increase the risk of injury.

Reviewer(s): Lucian Alikhani, Saskia Sterzl

Sources

Metalog. (2025, February 28). *HeartSelling: Verhandeln = fair handeln?* Metalog. <https://metalog.de/HeartSelling>

Schwägele, S. (2015). *Planspiel – Lernen – Lerntransfer: Eine subjektorientierte Analyse von Einflussfaktoren (ZMS-Schriftenreihe 7)*. Zentrum für Managementsimulation.